

WAYS TO DEVELOP MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

One of the methods that significantly affects the growth of a teacher's pedagogical skills, his qualifications, pedagogical abilities, pedagogical competence is continuous professional development. This article discusses the development of professional competencies in future specialists, methodological competence, its components, the tasks of methodological competence and ways to form this competence in primary school teachers.

Today, in the process of developing and improving the education system in accordance with international requirements, improving the professional competencies of primary school teachers remains one of the urgent issues. Because the primary education stage serves not only as a basis for the formation of knowledge and skills, but also as a basis for the personal development of students. In this process, in addition to pedagogical and psychological knowledge, it is of great importance for teachers to have effective management skills. Management skills allow teachers to effectively manage the classroom team, properly organize the educational process, effectively communicate with students, and resolve problem situations. In particular, ensuring discipline in the classroom, teaching taking into account the individual characteristics of students, and establishing cooperation with parents are important management tasks for primary school teachers.

The following methods can help to improve management competence in educational institutions:

- Developing and training teachers and other staff;
- Choosing a management model in accordance with the needs of students;
- Understanding good relationships with students and its importance;
- Working with requirements in action and listening to their opinions;
- Reviewing goals and analyzing them to improve efficiency in the decision-making process;
- Reflecting on the management characteristics that leaders have demonstrated against themselves;
- Learning new innovations and old skills in management;
- Communicating with students and teachers and paying attention to their feedback.

What is the importance of developing managerial competence? The importance of developing managerial competence is that it helps to create high efficiency and good relations with teachers and students in educational institutions, allows you to create convenient and good management models, helps to establish contact with students, and helps to manage innovative activities.

Professional pedagogical competence is considered a factor ensuring the high-quality organization of the activities of future primary school teachers. Today, it is becoming increasingly important to study the managerial competence of future primary school teachers. The insufficient development of the theoretical and methodological foundations of professional training of primary school teachers for the implementation of developmental education at school contradicts the argument that such readiness is put forward as a qualification requirement for the level of professional skills of teachers.

Higher education institutions are faced with an urgent task of improving the creative potential of future teachers, developing their personality, and ensuring their readiness to work in new conditions. In this regard, the following questions arise:

- How to organize the educational process in order to form an active attitude of students to educational and cognitive activity?
- How to prepare future primary school teachers to organize work with schoolchildren in adapted education?
- What educational technologies can be most effective?

In ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process, the formation of general educational skills of students is of great importance. In this regard, skills, qualifications, and competencies related to the subject of study are of particular importance.

The general nature of educational activities requires their formation on the basis of interdisciplinary connections. As a result of such connections, intersubject meta-skills and competencies are formed. In this process, students develop general cultural, knowledge-based and personal, self-development competencies. This approach serves to ensure continuity between all stages of the educational process. The motivating function is to direct the teacher's professional motivation, his desire to master the subject, the pedagogical, psychological, methodological knowledge necessary for effective methodological activities, and a positive attitude to the teacher's professional activities in general. Leaders with managerial competencies can work extensively in the good organization of educational processes, good relations with teachers and students, and management of innovative activities. This can lead to a high level of efficiency in the educational process of educational institutions.

- Convenient and good models are created in management. Along with increasing management competence, heads of educational institutions learn to create new, convenient and good management models, as well as learn to use their own characteristics in managing educational processes.

- Students' interest in learning increases. Increasing management competence helps to establish contact with students and allows them to increase their interest in learning and the effectiveness of future teaching. When good communication is established with students, teachers and other employees, an increase in the effectiveness and results of educational processes is observed.

- Innovative activities and innovations are observed. Increasing management competence increases the observation of innovative activities and innovations in an educational institution and allows them to be managed and mastered. This allows for the introduction of innovations in an educational institution, increasing efficiency and increasing interest in innovations.

- Good products are produced in management. Improving management competence allows for the improvement of the teaching and learning products of an educational institution. This allows for the production of good products in the educational institution, creating good teaching and learning opportunities for students.

- Increasing the value of employees in the educational institution.

The management function, on the one hand, ensures the management of the teacher's own activities in the educational process (planning, organization, adjustment, etc.), and on the other hand, the management of the activities of students in mastering subject knowledge and methods of activity aimed at the development of each student.

The development of communication skills in future primary school teachers is very important for effective teaching and student activity.

- the organic nature of practical training along with theoretical training in the formation of the management competence of a future primary school teacher is evident.

- the formation of management competence begins in a higher educational institution and continues in the workplace under the supervision of experienced teachers.

- the development of the abilities of future primary school teachers to adapt to the educational process, to the team, to resources, to adapt to themselves, to responsibility, to creativity.

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